

BREAST CANCER PREDICTION WITH GRADIENT BOOSTING CLASSIFIERS

Kingsley Ifeanyi Chibueze¹, Lucy Ifeyinwa Ezigbo², Anthony Kwubeghari²

¹Department of Computer Science & Mathematics, Godfrey Okoye University, Enugu, Nigeria

²Department of Computer Engineering, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria. Corresponding Authors E-mail: casperine1@gmail.com

Abstract

Breast cancer poses a significant global health challenge, being the most prevalent cancer in women and a leading cause of cancer-related mortality. With the increasing number of diagnoses, there is a pressing need for innovative approaches to enhance detection and treatment. This study explores the effectiveness of boosting algorithms, namely AdaBoost, XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM, in predicting breast cancer by leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) technologies. This research distinguishes itself from previous studies by focusing specifically on gradient boosting algorithms. The research utilizes datasets sourced from Kaggle, comprising 569 instances categorized into Benign (357) and Malignant (212) classes. Data preprocessing steps, such as feature selection and normalization, were performed to improve the model's learning ability and ensure that all features contribute fairly during training. Additionally, Hyperparameter tuning, including adjusting the learning rate, number of trees, and tree depth, was conducted to optimize the model's performance. Following training, various performance metrics including accuracy, sensitivity, precision, specificity, ROC-AUC, and confusion matrix were assessed. The results showed that AdaBoost achieved an accuracy of 97.37%, precision of 0.9545, recall of 0.9767, specificity of 0.9718, and an AUC-ROC of 0.9967. CatBoost achieved an accuracy of 97.49%, precision of 0.9756, recall of 0.9302, specificity of 0.9859, and an AUC-ROC of 0.9977. LightGBM achieved an accuracy of 96.49%, precision of 0.9535, recall of 0.9535, specificity of 0.9718, and an AUC-ROC of 0.9961. XGBoost achieved an accuracy of 95.61%, precision of 0.9524, recall of 0.9302, specificity of 0.9718, and an AUC-ROC of 0.9954. Among the algorithms tested, CatBoost stands out as the top performer. These results demonstrate the potential of ML techniques in breast cancer diagnosis and underscore the importance of ongoing research to address the evolving challenges in oncology. Furthermore, the integration of these algorithms into clinical decision support systems could enhance diagnostic accuracy and facilitate personalized treatment strategies, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Gradient Boosting Machines, Oncology, Healthcare AI, Clinical Decision Support Systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cancer remains one of the most formidable health challenges, with breast cancer emerging as the most prevalent type among women and the second leading cause of cancer-related deaths globally. Shockingly, breast cancer has now surpassed lung cancer as the most diagnosed form of cancer in women worldwide, underscoring the urgency for effective detection and treatment strategies. The past two decades have witnessed a staggering increase in cancer diagnoses, nearly doubling from an estimated 10 million in 2000 to 19.3 million in 2020 (WHO, 2020).

Tragically, one in every five individuals worldwide is projected to develop cancer in their lifetime, with forecasts indicating a further 50% increase in cancer diagnoses by 2040 compared to 2020. Similarly alarming, cancer-related deaths have surged from 6.2 million in 2000 to 10 million in 2020, highlighting the pressing need for improved diagnostic techniques and treatment modalities (Naji et al., 2021). The devastating toll of breast cancer on individuals, families, and communities underscores the urgent need for continued research, innovation, and comprehensive healthcare strategies to improve prevention, diagnosis, and treatment outcomes.

There are two primary classifications for cancer detection: benign and malignant. A malignant tumor, characterized by its rapid growth and invasive nature, poses a significant threat as it damages surrounding tissues by infiltrating them. In contrast, benign tumors are typically non-cancerous growths that do not exhibit invasive behavior and tend to grow slowly. Though benign tumors are generally not life-threatening, they can still cause discomfort or complications depending on their location and size (National Cancer Institute, 2020).

Early detection is pivotal in combatting breast cancer, with approximately half of cases going

undetected in screenings of women with dense breast tissue. Moreover, a quarter of breast cancer diagnoses occur within two years of screening, underscoring the critical importance of timely detection for optimal patient outcomes (Burnside et al., 2016).

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and convolutional neural networks (CNN) have emerged as transformative technologies in the healthcare sector (Masud et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2019). Leveraging AI and ML in breast cancer diagnosis holds immense promise, offering unparalleled capabilities in prediction, diagnosis, and cost reduction (Kamruzzaman, 2020; Min et al., 2015). Traditional computer-aided design (CAD) systems, while valuable, often rely on manually engineered features, limiting their overall efficacy (Bharati et al., 2020). However, the advent of deep learning-based techniques has revolutionized breast cancer detection, outperforming traditional ML methods and reducing the need for human intervention.

Recent studies have explored various approaches for breast cancer diagnosis, employing traditional methods, conventional machine learning algorithms, and advanced deep learning techniques. Traditional methods such as histopathological examination and imaging techniques (e.g., mammography and ultrasound) have shown efficacy in detecting breast cancer but are limited by human error and subjective interpretation (Elmore et al., 2017). Conventional machine learning models like Support Vector Machines (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), and Logistic Regression have demonstrated success in cancer classification but often struggle with overfitting, high computational costs, and limited interpretability when applied to complex or imbalanced datasets (Mathew, 2019; Mathew & Kumar, 2021). In contrast, recent advancements in deep learning,

particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have significantly enhanced breast cancer diagnosis by automating feature extraction and improving accuracy (Masud et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2019). However, these methods require large datasets and are computationally intensive, making them less suitable for smaller clinical settings. Despite the success of these methods, there remains a gap in utilizing boosting algorithms, such as CatBoost, LightGBM, XGBoost, and AdaBoost, for breast cancer classification. Boosting algorithms offer several advantages over traditional and deep learning approaches, including superior handling of class imbalances, missing values, and categorical features. They build strong predictive models by sequentially combining weak learners, which helps improve generalization and manage overfitting more effectively. Furthermore, boosting algorithms like CatBoost have built-in mechanisms for dealing with categorical features and missing values, thus enhancing their suitability for complex healthcare datasets. These methods excel in handling class imbalances, a common issue in breast cancer datasets where malignant cases are often underrepresented.

Despite these advantages, the application of boosting algorithms in breast cancer diagnosis remains limited. Most studies have predominantly focused on traditional classifiers or deep learning architectures, overlooking the potential of boosting methods to improve diagnostic accuracy and interpretability. The limited application of boosting algorithms in breast cancer diagnosis remains an underexplored area. Although boosting algorithms have demonstrated high predictive performance and robust handling of imbalanced datasets in other fields, their potential in breast cancer classification has yet to be fully realized. Addressing this gap is crucial, as these methods can offer improved

accuracy, interpretability, and efficiency over traditional models.

Therefore, this study aims to leverage state-of-the-art boosting algorithms, including, AdaBoost, XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM, to predict and diagnose breast cancer. By evaluating these algorithms based on accuracy, sensitivity, precision, specificity, ROC-AUC, and confusion matrix, we seek to identify the most effective approach for enhancing breast cancer diagnosis and ultimately improving patient outcomes. Additionally, the study seeks to assess the practical implications of integrating these boosting algorithms into clinical decision-making systems for breast cancer management. The findings could provide valuable insights for clinicians by improving the precision of diagnoses, reducing false positives/negatives, and offering a reliable tool to support personalized treatment strategies.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the literature review. Section 3 describes the materials and methods used in this research. The results and discussion for each Gradient Boosting model are provided in Section 4, along with a comparison table between the existing models and the newly developed model. Section 5 concludes the study by providing recommendations. Finally, Section 6 outlines future directions for ongoing research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous innovative technologies have emerged in the field of breast cancer diagnosis, contributing significantly to medical research. The following presents a summary of research endeavors in this domain. Kabiraj et al. (2020) utilized ensemble machine learning methods, XGBoost and Random Forest, to predict breast cancer using a dataset comprising 275 examples with 12 features. The analysis

yielded an accuracy of 74.73% with Random Forest and 73.63% with XGBoost. While this study introduced the use of ensemble methods, the small dataset size could limit the model's generalizability and increase the risk of overfitting. Kurian et al. (2022) conducted a comparative analysis of four machine learning classifiers: Random Forest, Decision Tree, AdaBoost, and Gradient Boosting (GB) on a larger dataset to classify benign and malignant tumors. Their findings revealed that GB exhibited superior performance with a classification accuracy of 95.82%. This study's strength lies in its broader dataset, but it did not explore potential issues like class imbalance. Gupta et al. (2021) emphasized the importance of early detection in fatal diseases like breast cancer and proposed a CatBoost-based ML algorithm. With an accuracy of 97.8%, CatBoost outperformed many traditional classifiers. However, the study lacked information on the type of dataset used, which is crucial for evaluating the model's efficacy in various scenarios. Amrane et al. (2018) compared Naive Bayes (NB) and K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) classifiers on a standard breast cancer dataset, achieving 97.51% accuracy with K-NN and 96.19% with NB. While the study highlights the effectiveness of these classifiers, it does not address the computational costs or the complexity associated with K-NN.

Sakri et al. (2018) aimed to enhance accuracy by combining ML techniques, including K-NNs, NB, and a reduced error pruning (REP) tree, with a feature selection algorithm (particle swarm optimization). Their methodology yielded accuracies of 70%, 76.3%, and 66.3% respectively, showing significant variation depending on the chosen model. This work illustrates the potential for integrating feature selection but highlights the challenge of achieving consistent results across different classifiers. Yolanda et al. (2019) reported a 74.14% accuracy using the GB

algorithm, showcasing its utility in breast cancer prediction. The study's limitation was its reliance on a single dataset, which could affect model robustness. Naji et al. (2021) applied five machine learning algorithms; Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, and KNN on the Breast Cancer Wisconsin Diagnostic dataset, with SVM achieving the highest accuracy of 97.2%. The strength of this study is its comprehensive comparative analysis, yet it lacks an exploration of ensemble methods that might further boost performance. Banu et al. (2018) examined Naive Bayes strategies, comparing Tree Augmented Naive Bayes (TAN) and Bayes Belief Network (BBN) classifiers. Using Gradient Boosting, BBN achieved 94.1% accuracy, while TAN attained 91.7% accuracy. The study highlights the potential of enhancing NB classifiers but lacks an analysis of computation time.

Chaurasia et al. (2018) applied Naive Bayes Classifier, Radial Basis Function Network, and Decision Tree Classifier algorithms on the WBCD dataset, with Naive Bayes achieving the highest accuracy of 97.36%. This study demonstrated the applicability of simple classifiers, though the omission of newer ensemble methods limits its relevance in contemporary research. Azar et al. (2021) presented a technique for breast cancer prediction using decision tree variants, single decision tree (SDT) and decision tree forest (DTF) achieving accuracies of 97.07% and 97.51% respectively. The work effectively demonstrates the impact of decision tree variants, but its limitation is the lack of external dataset validation. Ara et al. (2021) achieved an accuracy of 96.5% using Random Forest and SVM models, showcasing their effectiveness in this domain. However, the study lacks discussion on computational efficiency.

Ozcan et al. (2022) explored a wide range of algorithms, including SVM, Naive Bayes, Random Forest, Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbor, Logistic Regression, Multilayer Perceptron, Linear Discriminant Analysis, XGBoost, AdaBoost, and Gradient Boosting, with Gradient Boosting achieving the best accuracy of 99.12%. The study's strength lies in its extensive evaluation of algorithms, though the use of a single dataset might limit the generalizability of the findings. Khalid et al. (2023) employed six classification models; Linear Support Vector Classification, Support Vector Classification, K-Nearest Neighbor, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression; finding Random Forest to be the best performer with an accuracy of 96.49%. This study highlighted the robustness of Random Forest but did not delve into feature importance or explainability. Islam et al. (2017) reported a training accuracy of 99.68% using SVM, contributing valuable insights into machine learning techniques for healthcare applications. However, the study lacked a test set evaluation, which is necessary to confirm the model's practical performance. Thomas et al. (2020) evaluated various algorithms, with Artificial Neural Networks achieving the highest accuracy of 97.85%. The study's deep learning approach is promising, but the high computational cost and potential for overfitting are concerns not addressed in the work.

Irmawati et al. (2020) employed Deep Learning with Adam's optimization, resulting in a final system accuracy of 96%. The study effectively used DL techniques, though the lack of comparison with other optimizers reduces the scope of the findings. Kohli et al. (2018) utilized Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Decision Tree, and AdaBoost, achieving an accuracy of 98.57%. This study's robust methodology is noteworthy, but it did not address hyperparameter tuning comprehensively. Ojha and Goel (2017) explored classification and

clustering algorithms, with Decision Tree and SVM models achieving an accuracy of 81%. Despite the relatively low accuracy, the study contributes by examining clustering methods, which are often overlooked. Das and Biswas (2019) proposed an ensemble voting approach combining the predictions from five distinct ML models: Random Forest, Naive Bayes, and SVM. This ensemble method attained an accuracy rate of 99.28%, showcasing the potential for improving prediction performance by combining multiple classifiers. The main limitation is the increased computational complexity associated with ensemble models. Islam et al. (2022) collected data from three hospitals and employed Decision Tree, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, and XGBoost algorithms, reporting an accuracy of 94% for both Random Forest and XGBoost. This study's strength is its use of real-world data, but the omission of deep learning models leaves room for further exploration. Abed et al. (2016) proposed a hybrid approach combining a genetic algorithm and k-nearest neighbor, yielding an accuracy of 99%. This study effectively demonstrates the utility of hybrid approaches but lacks a detailed discussion on parameter selection and algorithm complexity.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the methodology employed for breast cancer prediction, as illustrated in Figure 1. The process initiates with the collection of a dataset comprising individuals diagnosed with breast cancer. Subsequently, the gathered data undergoes preprocessing procedures aimed at ensuring data quality and enhancing the effectiveness of the training process. The preprocessed data serve as input for gradient boosting algorithms. The training process continues iteratively until the error between the actual and predicted values reaches a minimal and acceptable threshold. The entire implementation of this methodology is carried out using the machine

learning toolbox available within Google Colaboratory. Additionally, libraries such as pandas, numpy, and sklearn are imported. To

validate the methodology, a comparative analysis is performed to identify the most suitable algorithm for breast cancer prediction.

3.1 Data collection

Data for this study was sourced from the Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) Data Set, available in the Kaggle repository. It contains 569 instances categorized into two

classes: Benign (357) and Malignant (212), as depicted in Figure 2. The dataset comprises 32 attributes utilized in this analysis as depicted in Table 1. It includes breast cancer cases from women aged between 29 and 89 years old.

Figure 2: Wisconsin Breast Cancer Target Distribution

Table 1: Dataset Features and Description

S/N	Attribute	Description	S/N	Attribute	Description
1	ID	Unique identifier for each patient (not used for prediction).	17	Smoothness SE	Standard error of smoothness.
2	Diagnosis	Target variable: B = Benign, M = Malignant	18	Compactness SE	Standard error of compactness.
3	Radius Mean	Mean radius (average distance from center to perimeter).	19	Concavity SE	Standard error of concavity.

4	Texture Mean	Mean texture (standard deviation of grayscale values).	20	Concave Points SE	Standard error of concave points.
5	Perimeter Mean	Mean perimeter (distance around the boundary).	21	Symmetry SE	Standard error of symmetry.
6	Area Mean	Mean area of the cell nucleus.	22	Fractal Dimension SE	Standard error of fractal dimension.
7	Smoothness Mean	Mean smoothness (local variation in radius lengths).	23	Radius Worst	Worst value (largest) of radius.
8	Compactness Mean	Mean compactness $\frac{\text{Perimeter}^2}{\text{Area}}$	24	Texture Worst	Worst value of texture.
9	Concavity Mean	Mean concavity (severity of concave portions of the contour).	25	Perimeter Worst	Worst value of perimeter.
10	Concave Points Mean	Mean concave points (number of inward curves).	26	Area Worst	Worst value of area.
11	Symmetry Mean	Mean symmetry of the cell nucleus.	27	Smoothness Worst	Worst value of smoothness.
12	Fractal Dimension Mean	Mean fractal dimension (complexity of the boundary).	28	Compactness Worst	Worst value of compactness.
13	Radius SE	Standard error of radius.	29	Concavity Worst	Worst value of concavity.
14	Texture SE	Standard error of texture.	30	Concave Points Worst	Worst value of concave points.
15	Perimeter SE	Standard error of perimeter.	31	Symmetry Worst	Worst value of symmetry.
16	Area SE	Standard error of area.	32	Fractal Dimension Worst	Worst value of fractal dimension.

3.2 Data preprocessing:

The dataset primarily comprises numerical values and does not contain any missing data. Consequently, preprocessing steps such as handling missing values and encoding categorical variables are deemed unnecessary. However, other preprocessing methods, such as feature selection and normalization, are still conducted. Feature selection involves identifying and keeping only the most relevant features in a dataset while removing those that

are redundant or irrelevant. This can be done by examining correlations between features and using statistical tests to determine which features have the strongest relationship with the target variable. This helps the model learn better and faster. Normalization involves adjusting the values of different features so they are on a similar scale. This prevents large values from dominating the learning process and helps the model understand each feature equally. It can be done by scaling the values to a range like 0 to 1 or by making the values have an average of zero and a similar spread.

Normalization ensures that all features contribute fairly when training the model.

After preprocessing, the dataset is split into training, validation, and test sets in the proportions of 70:15:15. The training set is used to train the model, the validation set is used for hyperparameter tuning to optimize model performance, and the test set is used to evaluate the final model performance after training and tuning. This split helps assess the model's performance and prevents overfitting.

3.3 Gradient Boosting Machines

Gradient Boosting Machines (GBMs) are a type of machine learning algorithms widely used for regression and classification tasks. The basic idea of boosting is to combine the predictions of many weak classifiers to create a strong overall model (Natekin & Knoll, 2020). In simpler terms, GBMs build a series of models, each one correcting the mistakes of the previous one, until a highly accurate final model is achieved. This approach helps improve the model's performance and predictive accuracy.

$$F(x) = \sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_m h_m(x) \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_m(x) \\ = F_{m-1}(x) + \gamma_m h_m(x) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

3.3.1 Adaboost

AdaBoost, short for Adaptive Boosting, is one of the earliest algorithms to create a powerful classifier from weaker ones. In AdaBoost, each weak learner focuses on different aspects of the data, and their predictions are combined to create a stronger overall model. After each round of learning, the algorithm adjusts the weights assigned to the training data, giving more weight to the observations that were

incorrectly classified and less weight to those that were classified correctly. This adaptive adjustment process helps AdaBoost prioritize the data points that are more challenging to classify, leading to the creation of a robust and accurate final classifier (Ali et al., 2021).

$$F(x) = \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t f_t(x) \quad (3)$$

3.3.2 XGBoost

XGBoost is a highly efficient and versatile machine learning algorithm introduced in 2016. It excels in predictive accuracy and speed due to its innovative regularization techniques, which helps prevent overfitting. Regularization techniques in XGBoost, such as L1 (Lasso) and L2 (Ridge) regularization, penalize complex models by adding regularization terms to the objective function during training (Chen & Guestrin, 2016). These terms discourage the model from becoming overly complex and overfitting the training data.

$$F(x) = \sum_{m=1}^M f_m(x) \quad (4)$$

3.3.3 CatBoost

CatBoost is a machine learning algorithm designed to prevent overfitting by using target-based statistics. It calculates the average value based on previous data points to avoid data leakage. A notable feature is its built-in permutation technique for handling categorical columns, known as One Hot Max Size (OHMS). CatBoost efficiently handles the exponential growth of feature combinations using a greedy method at each tree split. It constructs symmetric trees and supports categorical columns, making it effective for a wide range of machine learning tasks (Dorogush et al, 2017).

$$F(x) = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(x) \quad (5)$$

3.3.4 LightGBM

LightGBM is a gradient boosting framework that works by growing trees vertically instead of horizontally, using a technique called leaf-wise growth. It splits the tree leaf-wise rather than level-wise, focusing on the leaves with the highest loss change. This approach results in faster training times and lower memory usage. Additionally, LightGBM uses a histogram-based algorithm to bucket continuous features into discrete bins, reducing the computational cost of finding the best split points (Ke et al, 2017). Overall, LightGBM efficiently builds

decision trees and achieves high accuracy with minimal resources.

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{k=1}^M \omega_k \cdot f_k(x_i) \quad (6)$$

3.4 Hyperparameter Tuning

Additionally, hyperparameters are tuned to further optimize the model's performance as displayed in Table 2. The key hyperparameters for tuning in Gradient Boosting Machines involve adjusting the learning rate, the number of trees, and the maximum depth of each tree.

Table 2: Table of Hyperparameter settings of each of the boosting algorithms

Algorithm	Hyperparameter	Description	Optimal Value
AdaBoost	n_estimators	Number of weak learners to combine	50
	learning_rate	Weight applied to each classifier	0.1
CatBoost	iterations	Number of boosting iterations	1000
	learning_rate	Step size for the boosting process	0.03
	Depth	Depth of the tree	6
	l2_leaf_reg	L2 regularization term	3
XGBoost	n_estimators	Number of boosting rounds	500
	learning_rate	Step size shrinkage	0.1
	max_depth	Maximum depth of a tree	5
	subsample	Fraction of samples used for training	0.8
LightGBM	num_leaves	Number of leaves in one tree	31
	max_depth	Maximum depth of a tree	-1 (no limit)
	learning_rate	Step size for the boosting process	0.05
	n_estimators	Number of boosting iterations	1000

3.5 Training of the Gradient Boosting Machines

In gradient boosting algorithms such as CatBoost, AdaBoost, LightGBM, and XGBoost, dataset training involves iteratively constructing an ensemble of weak learners to form a robust model. Initially, the algorithm fits a base model to the data, predicting the target variable's residuals. Subsequent models are then trained to predict these residuals,

gradually reducing prediction errors. This iterative process continues until the specified number of weak learners is reached or until further iterations fail to improve performance. Each model's predictions are weighted and combined to produce the final ensemble model, optimizing predictive accuracy through sequential refinement.

3.6 Performance Evaluation Metrics

Accuracy is a standard metric for classification algorithms, quantifies the ratio of correct predictions (both true positives and true negatives) to the total predictions made by the model.

Formula:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (7)$$

Precision is another critical metric, denotes the proportion of correctly predicted positive instances among all instances predicted as positive, shedding light on the model's capability to avoid false positives.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives (TP)}}{\text{True Positives (TP)} + \text{False Positives (FP)}} \quad (8)$$

Recall measures the proportion of actual positive instances that were correctly predicted

by the model. It focuses on identifying all true positive instances and minimizing false negatives.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{(TP)}{(TP) + (FN)} \quad (9)$$

Specificity measures the proportion of actual negatives that are correctly identified by the model.

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{(TN)}{(TN) + (FP)} \quad (10)$$

Confusion matrix stands as a pivotal metric, it presents the counts of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) in a structured format, which aids in understanding the model's performance across different classes.

Table 3: Structure of the Confusion Matrix

	Predicted Positive (Malignant)	Predicted Negative (Benign)
Actual Positive (Malignant)	True Positives (TP)	False Negatives (FN)
Actual Negative (Benign)	False Positives (FP)	True Negatives (TN)

The Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC) is a widely used metric for evaluating the performance of classification models, The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve is a graphical representation of the trade-off between sensitivity (true positive rate) and specificity (false positive rate) as the decision threshold of the classifier is varied. It is plotted with: It is plotted with:

True Positive Rate (TPR) on the Y-axis (also known as Recall)

$$\text{TPR} = \frac{(TP)}{(TP) + (FN)} \quad (11)$$

False Positive Rate (FPR) on the X-axis:

$$\text{FPR} = \frac{(FP)}{(FP) + (TN)} \quad (12)$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Following the application of Gradient Boosting Machines (GBMs) on the Breast Cancer Wisconsin Diagnostic dataset, we employed various performance metrics for model evaluation and comparison. In the context of breast cancer prediction, Accuracy measures the overall effectiveness of the model in correctly identifying both benign and

malignant tumors. Precision focuses on the model's ability to correctly identify malignant tumors among all tumors predicted as malignant. Recall measures the model's ability to identify all actual malignant tumors. Specificity evaluates the model's ability to correctly identify benign tumors among all tumors that are actually benign. Following training, the subsequent results displayed in Table 4 were obtained.

Table 4: Training Reports of the models

Algorithms	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Specificity	AUC-ROC
AdaBoost	97.37%	0.9545	0.9767	0.9718	0.9967
CatBoost	97.49%	0.9756	0.9302	0.9859	0.9977
LightGBM	96.49%	0.9535	0.9535	0.9718	0.9961
XGBoost	95.61%	0.9524	0.9302	0.9718	0.9954

Figure 3: Results of the Models

In the context of breast cancer detection, the confusion matrix helps in evaluating how well a model differentiates between benign (non-cancerous) and malignant (cancerous) tumors.

Each component of the confusion matrix provides insight into the model's ability to make accurate predictions and informs decisions regarding its deployment in clinical

practice. Below, Figures 4 through 7 display the confusion matrix, providing a detailed insight into the model's classification performance

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix for AdaBoost

Figure 5: Confusion Matrix for CatBoost

Figure 6: Confusion Matrix for XGBoost

Figure 7: Confusion Matrix for LightGBM

Lastly, the Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC-ROC) served as a performance metric to evaluate the model's ability to differentiate

between classes. A higher AUC-ROC value signifies superior discrimination ability of the model as displayed in Figure 8.

Figure 8: ROC Curve for the four models

4.2 Discussion

The findings from the study reveal that CatBoost and AdaBoost outperformed LightGBM and XGBoost in terms of accuracy. Following hyperparameter tuning, CatBoost exhibited the highest accuracy of 97.49%, trailed by AdaBoost at 97.37%, LightGBM at 96.49%, and XGBoost at 95.61%. Additionally, CatBoost demonstrated superior performance across other key metrics such as precision, specificity, and AUC-ROC compared to AdaBoost, LightGBM, and

XGBoost. Analyzing the confusion matrix, CatBoost displayed the highest counts of true positives and true negatives, indicating a greater number of correct predictions. Moreover, it exhibited the lowest counts of false positives and false negatives, suggesting fewer incorrect predictions. Overall, the results suggest that CatBoost emerges as the most effective machine-learning algorithm for this specific study. Below, Table 5 presents a comparison of available prediction machine-learning models for breast cancer.

Table 5: Comparative Analysis

Author	Dataset Name	Algorithm Name	Accuracy (%)
Kabiraj et al. (2020)	UCI BCD	RF, XGBoost	74.73%,73.63%
Dutta, Bandyopadhyay, (2020)	& WBCD	AdaBoost, GB	96.81%,97.34%

Author(s)	Dataset	Classifiers	Performance (%)
Prastyo et al. (2020)	WBCD	GB, AdaBoost	95.96%, 97.19%, 95.96%
Gupta et al. (2021)	WBCD	CatBoost, DT, KNN	97.80%, 97.08%, 95.60%, 97%
Assegie et al. (2021)	WBCD	DT, AdaBoost	90.20%, 96.50%
Islam et al. (2022)	WBCD	GB, KNN	95.34%, 75.96%
Mangukiya et al. (2022)	WBCD	XGB, AdaBoost	98.24%, 94.73%
Rahman et al. (2023)	WBCD	GB, AdaBoost	95.80%, 97.20%, 98.60%
Our Work	WBCD	AdaBoost, CatBoost, LightGBM, XGBoost	97.37%, 97.49%, 96.49%, 95.61%

In previous research on the WBCD dataset, CatBoost, XGBoost, and AdaBoost classifiers outperformed other classifiers. Additionally, Gradient Boosting (GB) demonstrated comparable performance in earlier studies. Overall, the findings suggest that CatBoost is an equally effective classifier for predicting breast cancer on the WBCD dataset, despite its lesser usage due to its complexity.

4.3 The Breast Cancer Detection Model

The CatBoost model, which has demonstrated superior performance compared to other models, is utilized for effective breast cancer detection and is integrated into a Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS). When a patient visits the clinic for breast cancer evaluation, they undergo diagnostic imaging, such as a mammogram. Relevant clinical and demographic data are recorded during this process. The patient's diagnostic features, derived from the Wisconsin Breast Cancer

Diagnostic (WBCD) dataset, consist of 30 attributes extracted from the imaging results and entered into the CDSS. Once the data is collected, it undergoes preprocessing to ensure it aligns with the format used during the model training. After preprocessing, the data is fed into the CatBoost model, which has been specifically trained on the WBCD dataset. The model then predicts whether the tumor is benign or malignant, providing a probability score that indicates the model's confidence in its prediction. For example, the model might output a prediction of 0.85 for benign and 0.15 for malignant, suggesting a higher likelihood of the tumor being benign. The prediction results, along with their associated probability scores, are displayed on the CDSS interface. The system highlights whether the tumor is more likely to be benign or malignant, thereby assisting healthcare professionals in making informed clinical decisions based on the model's analysis. Figure 9 describes how the Breast Cancer Detection Model is utilized for the effective detection of Breast Cancer disease.

Figure 9: Flowchart of the Breast Cancer Detection Model

5. CONCLUSIONS

The rising global burden of breast cancer has created an urgent need for more effective and accurate diagnostic tools. This study was conducted to address this pressing issue by exploring machine learning models that can predict and diagnose breast cancer. The primary objective was to evaluate state-of-the-art boosting algorithms, namely, AdaBoost, XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM, based on their performance metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, precision, specificity, ROC-AUC, and confusion matrix, with the goal of identifying the most effective model for enhancing breast cancer diagnosis and

ultimately improving patient outcomes. The research highlights the urgent need for accurate diagnostic tools due to the increasing global burden of cancer. A detailed review of existing literature reveals that various machine learning algorithms have been investigated for breast cancer prediction, each showing promising results. In this study, the models; AdaBoost, XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost were employed. Among these, CatBoost emerged as the most effective, achieving a remarkable accuracy rate of 97.49%. The findings demonstrate that boosting algorithms, particularly CatBoost, offer substantial improvements in breast cancer prediction and have the potential to significantly impact

clinical decision-making and patient management. As the best-performing model, CatBoost was integrated into a Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS) and utilized the WBCD dataset for accurate classification of benign and malignant tumors. This system can serve as an invaluable tool for clinicians, assisting in timely and accurate decision-making.

Despite the promising results, several limitations should be acknowledged. One key limitation is the relatively small sample size of the WBCD dataset, which may not fully represent the diverse characteristics of a larger patient population. This could hinder the model's generalizability when applied to a broader demographic. Additionally, the dataset primarily includes data from a homogenous population, which may not reflect diverse ethnicities and genetic variations that could influence breast cancer diagnosis. The research also underscores the importance of continuous innovation and advancement in healthcare analytics to address the evolving challenges in cancer detection and treatment. Future research should consider incorporating larger and more diverse datasets to improve model generalizability and robustness. Furthermore, it would be beneficial to explore hybrid models and advanced deep learning techniques to mitigate potential overfitting and enhance predictive performance. Based on the findings, it is recommended to further explore and validate the efficacy of Gradient Boosting Machines in real-world clinical settings. Collaborative efforts between healthcare professionals and data scientists are essential for integrating machine learning models into clinical practice seamlessly.

6. FUTURE WORK

Ongoing research should prioritize collecting and incorporating diverse datasets that reflect a wide range of ethnicities and genetic

variations, as these factors can significantly influence breast cancer diagnosis. This will help to ensure that AI models are robust and generalizable across different populations. Additionally, the development of user-friendly interfaces and decision support systems can facilitate the adoption of AI-assisted diagnostics in healthcare settings.

Furthermore, longitudinal studies and clinical trials are warranted to evaluate the long-term impact of AI-based breast cancer detection on patient outcomes, including survival rates and quality of life. By fostering interdisciplinary collaborations and leveraging cutting-edge technologies, we can advance the field of oncology and improve healthcare delivery for patients worldwide.

References

- Abed, B. M., Shaker, K., Jalab, H. A., Shaker, H., Mansoor, A. M., Alwan, A. F., & Al-Gburi, I. S. (2016). A hybrid classification algorithm approach for breast cancer diagnosis. In 2016 IEEE Industrial Electronics and Applications Conference (IEACon) (pp. 269–274).
- Amrane, M., Oukid, S., Gagawa, I., & Ensari, T. (2018). Breast cancer classification using machine learning. In 2018 Electric Electronics, Computer Science, Biomedical Engineerings' Meeting (EBBT) (pp. 1–4).
- Ali, A., Hossain, M. A., & Miah, M. J. (2021). A review of boosting techniques for class imbalance problem. *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2021.07.004>
- Ara, S., Das, A., & Dey, A. (2021). Malignant and benign breast cancer classification using machine learning algorithms. In 2021 International Conference on

- Artificial Intelligence (ICAI) (pp. 97–101).
- Assegie, T. A., Tulasi, R. L., & Kumar, N. K. (2021). Breast cancer prediction model with decision tree and adaptive boosting. *Journal of Cancer Science and Research*, 10(1), 184-194.
- Azar, A. T., & El-Metwally, S. M. (2012). Decision tree classifiers for automated medical diagnosis. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 23(7–8), 2387–2403.
- Banu, A. B., & Subramanian, P. T. (2018). Comparison of Bayes classifiers for breast cancer classification. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention (APJCP)*, 19(10), 2917–2920.
- Bharati, S., Podder, P., & Mondal, M. R. H. (2020). Artificial neural network based breast cancer screening: A comprehensive review. *International Journal of Computer Information Systems and Industrial Management Applications*, 12, 125–137.
- Burnside, E. S., Liu, J., Wu, Y., Onitilo, A. A., McCarty, C. A., Page, C. D., et al. (2016). Comparing Mammography Abnormality Features to Genetic Variants in the Prediction of Breast Cancer in Women Recommended for Breast Biopsy. *Academic Radiology*, 23(1), 62–69.
- Chaurasia, V., Pal, S., & Tiwari, B. (2018). Prediction of benign and malignant breast cancer using data mining techniques. *Journal of Algorithms & Computational Technology*, 12(2), 119–126.
- Chen, M., Yang, J., Hu, L., Hossain, M. S., & Muhammad, G. (2018). Urban healthcare big data system based on crowdsourced and cloud-based air quality indicators. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 56(11), 14–20.
- Chen, T., & Guestrin, C. (2016). Xgboost: A scalable tree boosting system. *CoRR*, abs/1603.02754. Retrieved from <http://arxiv.org/abs/1603.02754>
- Das, S., & Biswas, D. (2019). Prediction of breast cancer using ensemble learning. In 2019 5th International Conference on Advances in Electrical Engineering (ICAEE) (pp. 804–808).
- Dutta, S., & Bandyopadhyay, S. K. (2020). Early Breast Cancer Prediction using Artificial Intelligence Methods. *Journal of Environmental Research and Reports*, 58329.
- Dorogush, A. V., Gulin, A., Gusev, G., Kazeev, N., Prokhorenkova, L. O., & Vorobev, A. (2017). Fighting biases with dynamic boosting. *CoRR*, abs/1706.0.
- Fan, J., Wu, Y., Yuan, M., Page, D., Liu, J., Ong, I. M., et al. (2016). Structure-leveraged methods in breast cancer risk prediction. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 17(1), 2956-2970.
- Gupta, H., Kumar, P., Saurabh, S., Mishra, K., Appasani, B., Pati, A., et al. (2021). Category Boosting Machine Learning Algorithm for Breast Cancer Prediction. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 66(3), 201–206.
- Islam, M. M., Iqbal, H., Haque, M. R., & Hasan, M. K. (2017). Prediction of breast cancer using support vector machine and k-nearest neighbors. In 2017 IEEE Region 10 Humanitarian Technology Conference (R10- HTC) (pp. 226–229).

- Islam, M. S., Ashikuzzaman, M., & Mojumdar, J. (2022). Breast Cancer Detection using Machine Learning Techniques. *Journal of Health Information Science and Systems*, 184(39).
- Islam, T., Kundu, A., Islam Khan, N., Bonik, C. C., Akter, F., & Islam, M. J. (2022). Machine learning approaches to predict breast cancer: Bangladesh perspective. In *Ubiquitous Intelligent Systems* (pp. 291–305). Springer Nature Singapore.
- Irmawati, F., Ernawan, M., Fakhreldin, M., & Saryoko, A. (2023). Deep learning method based for breast cancer classification. In *2023 International Conference on Information Technology Research and Innovation (ICITRI)* (pp. 13–16).
- Kabiraj, S., Raihan, M., Alvi, N., Afrin, M., Akter, L., Sohagi, S. A., & Podder, E. (2020). Breast cancer risk prediction using XGBoost and random forest algorithm. In *2020 11th International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)* (pp. 1–4).
- Kamruzzaman, M. M. (2020). Architecture of smart health care system using artificial intelligence. In *Proceedings of the 2020 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia & Expo Workshops (ICMEW)* (pp. 1–6). London, UK.
- Ke, G., Meng, Q., Finley, T., Wang, T., Chen, W., Ma, W., Ye, Q., & Liu, T.-Y. (2017). Lightgbm: A highly efficient gradient boosting decision tree. In I. Guyon, U. V. Luxburg, S. Bengio, H. Wallach, R. Fergus, S. Vishwanathan, & R. Garnett (Eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (Vol. 30). Curran Associates, Inc. Retrieved from <https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2017/file/6449f44a102fde848669bdd9eb6b76fa-Paper.pdf>
- Khalid, A., Mehmood, A., Alabrah, A., Alkhamees, B. F., Amin, F., AlSalman, H., & Choi, G. S. (2023). Breast cancer detection and prevention using machine learning. *Diagnostics*, 13(19). Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-4418/13/19/3113>
- Kohli, P. S., & Arora, S. (2018). Application of machine learning in disease prediction. In *2018 4th International Conference on Computing Communication and Automation (ICCCA)* (pp. 1–4).
- Kurian, B., & Jyothi, V. L. (2022). Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Methods for Breast Cancer Classification in Genetic Sequences. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 1–6.
- Mangukiya, M., Vaghani, A., & Savani, M. (2022). Breast Cancer Detection with Machine Learning. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, 2321-9653.
- Masud, M., Rashed, A. E. E., & Hossain, M. S. (2020). Convolutional neural network-based models for diagnosis of breast cancer. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 5.
- Mathew, T. E. (2019). A comparative study of the performance of different support vector machine kernels in breast cancer diagnosis. *International Journal of Information and Computer Sciences*, 6(6), 432–441.

- Mathew, T. (2019). A logistic regression with recursive feature elimination model for breast cancer diagnosis. *International Journal of Emerging Technology*, 10(3), 55–63.
- Mathew, T. E., & Kumar, K. S. A. (2021). A modified-weighted-k-nearest neighbour and cuckoo search hybrid model for breast cancer classification. *Indian Journal of Computer Science and Engineering*, 12(1), 166–177.
- Mathew, T. E. (2022). An optimized extremely randomized tree model for breast cancer classification. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 100(16).
- Min, W., Bao, B.-K., Xu, C., & Hossain, M. S. (2015). Cross-platform multi-modal topic modeling for personalized inter-platform recommendation. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, 17(10), 1787–1801.
- Naji, M. A., Filali, S. E., Aarika, K., Benlahmar, E. H., Abdelouahid, R. A., & Debauche, O. (2021). Machine learning algorithms for breast cancer prediction and diagnosis. *Procedia Computer Science*, 191, 487–492.
- Natekin, A., & Knoll, A. (2020). Gradient boosting machines, a tutorial. *Frontiers in Neurorobotics*, 7, 21. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbot.2020.00021>
- National Cancer Institute. (2020). Types of cancer. Retrieved from <https://www.cancer.gov>
- Ojha, U., & Goel, S. (2017). A study on prediction of breast cancer recurrence using data mining techniques. In 2017 7th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering - Confluence (pp. 527–530).
- Ozcan, I., Aydin, H., & Cetinkaya, A. (2022). Comparison of classification success rates of different machine learning algorithms in the diagnosis of breast cancer. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention (APJCP)*, 23, 3287–3297.
- Prastyo, P. H., Paramartha, G. Y., Pakpahan, M. S. M., & Ardiyanto, I. (2020). Predicting Breast Cancer: A Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms. Volume 3.
- Rahman, M. M., Ferdousi, Z., Saha, P., & Mayuri, R. (2023). A Machine Learning Approach to Predict Breast Cancer Using Boosting Classifiers. *Indian Journal of Computer Science and Engineering*, 14, 409-415.
- Sakri, S. B., Rashid, N. B. A., & Zain, Z. M. (2018). Particle swarm optimization feature selection for breast cancer recurrence prediction. *IEEE Access*, 6, 29637–29647.
- Thomas, T., Pradhan, N., & Dhaka, V. S. (2020). Comparative analysis to predict breast cancer using machine learning algorithms: A survey. In 2020 International Conference on Inventive Computation Technologies (ICICT) (pp. 192–196).
- WHO. (2020). Breast cancer. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/cancer/prevention/diagnosis-screening/breast-cancer/en/>
- Zhang, G., Huang, K., Cui, W., Zhou, Y., & Zhang, Z. (2021). Breast Cancer Risk Prediction Using XGBoost and Random Forest Algorithm. In 2020 11th International Conference on Computing, Communication and

Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)
(pp. 1–4).

Zhang, Y., Ma, X., Zhang, J., Hossain, M. S.,
Muhammad, G., & Amin, S. U.
(2019). Edge intelligence in the
cognitive internet of things: improving
sensitivity and interactivity. *IEEE
Network*, 33(3), 58–64.

